

Deuteration and Macromolecular Crystallisation (DEMAX): Chemical Deuteration Analytical Data

Proposal ID	6CX55ZYK
Principle Investigator	Katherine Thompson
Structure/Description	<p style="text-align: center;">77,5/83,1% D across oxononanoyl chain, including/excluding aldehydic hydrogen</p> <p style="text-align: center;">18,2% D across entire molecule</p> <p>1-palmitoyl-2-(9-oxononanoyl)-<i>d</i>₁₄-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine</p>
Code	OB_135
Producer	Anna Leung & Oliver Bogojevic
Mass	15,98 mg
% Deuteration	18,2% across entire molecule (77,5% in the oxononanoyl-chain including aldehydic hydrogen; 83,1% in the oxononanoyl-chain excluding aldehydic hydrogen)
Analyses	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ¹ H NMR spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> ¹³ C NMR spectrum <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mass spectrum <input type="checkbox"/> TLC plate <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____

Figure 1. ^1H NMR spectrum of 1-palmitoyl-2-(9-oxononanoyl)- d_{14} -sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (OB_135, POND₁₄PC) in CDCl_3 (400 MHz).

Figure 2. ^1H NMR spectrum of 1-palmitoyl-2-(9-oxononanoyl)- d_{14} -sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (OB_135, POND₁₄PC) in CDCl_3 (400 MHz) (expansion).

Figure 3. ESI-MS(+) of 1-palmitoyl-2-(9-oxononanoyl)- d_{14} -sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (OB_135, POND₁₄PC): m/z calculated for $C_{33}H_{50}D_{14}NO_9P$ $[M+H]^+$ as 664,5; found: 664,4 $[M+H]^+$, other adducts: 681,4 $[M+NH_4]^+$, 686,4 $[M+Na]^+$, 696,4 $[M+CH_3OH+H]^+$; additional adducts not assigned 716,4-739,4 amu (assigned as product adducts due to isotopologue pattern).

Calculation of % Deuteration from MS Isotope Distribution									
Note: Always label the lowest m/z peak as Peak No. 1 & increment each subsequent peak by 1 m/z unit									
Parent Ion Peak No.	Theoretical % D for Peak	Peak Area	Corrected Peak Area	Contribution of Peak to Overall % D	¹³ C Isotopic Distribution from ChemDraw:		Theoretical % D for Peak	Corrected Peak Area	Amount (%) of compound at Theoretical % D
1	14,1	2,5000E+00	2,5000E+00	0,8	¹³ C # 2	35,7	14,1	2,5000E+00	5,5
2	15,6	5,7000E+00	4,8075E+00	1,7	¹³ C # 3	3,5	15,6	4,8075E+00	10,6
3	17,2	1,3400E+01	1,1278E+01	4,3	Total Corrected Area of all Isotopic Peaks		17,2	1,1278E+01	24,9
4	18,8	2,2000E+01	1,7017E+01	7,0			20,3	7,8770E+00	17,4
5	20,3	1,6200E+01	7,8770E+00	3,5	Average % Deuteration of Molecule		21,9	1,8466E+00	4,1
6	21,9	8,4000E+00	1,8466E+00	0,9			4,5325E+01	0,0	0,0000E+00
7			0,0000E+00	0,0	Error = +/- 2 %		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
8			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
9			0,0000E+00	0,0	Input Data		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
10			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
11			0,0000E+00	0,0	Calculated		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
12			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
13			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
14			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
15			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
16			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
17			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
18			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
19			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
20			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
21			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
22			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
23			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
24			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
25			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
26			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
27			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
28			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
29			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
30			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	

Figure 4. Calculation of deuteration percentage of 1-palmitoyl-2-(9-oxononanoyl)-d₁₄-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine, POND₁₄PC, (OB_135) based on ESI-MS (across entire molecule).

Calculation of % Deuteration from MS Isotope Distribution									
Note: Always label the lowest m/z peak as Peak No. 1 & increment each subsequent peak by 1 m/z unit									
Parent Ion Peak No.	Theoretical % D for Peak	Peak Area	Corrected Peak Area	Contribution of Peak to Overall % D	¹³ C Isotopic Distribution from ChemDraw:		Theoretical % D for Peak	Corrected Peak Area	Amount (%) of compound at Theoretical % D
1	60,0	2,5000E+00	2,5000E+00	3,3	¹³ C # 2	35,7	60,0	2,5000E+00	5,5
2	66,7	5,7000E+00	4,8075E+00	7,1	¹³ C # 3	3,5	66,7	4,8075E+00	10,6
3	73,3	1,3400E+01	1,1278E+01	18,2	Total Corrected Area of all Isotopic Peaks		73,3	1,1278E+01	24,9
4	80,0	2,2000E+01	1,7017E+01	30,0			86,7	7,8770E+00	17,4
5	86,7	1,6200E+01	7,8770E+00	15,1	Average % Deuteration of Molecule		93,3	1,8466E+00	4,1
6	93,3	8,4000E+00	1,8466E+00	3,8			4,5325E+01	0,0	0,0000E+00
7			0,0000E+00	0,0	Error = +/- 2 %		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
8			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
9			0,0000E+00	0,0	Input Data		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
10			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
11			0,0000E+00	0,0	Calculated		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
12			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
13			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
14			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
15			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
16			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
17			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
18			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
19			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
20			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
21			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
22			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
23			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
24			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
25			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
26			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
27			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
28			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
29			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	
30			0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0	0,0	

Figure 5. Calculation of deuteration percentage of the hydrogen atoms in the oxononanoyl-chain of POND₁₄PC based on ESI-MS of OB_135 (including aldehydic hydrogen).

Calculation of % Deuteration from MS Isotope Distribution									
Note: Always label the lowest m/z peak as Peak No. 1 & increment each subsequent peak by 1 m/z unit									
Parent Ion Peak No.	Theoretical % D for Peak	Peak Area	Corrected Peak Area	Contribution of Peak to Overall % D	¹³ C Isotopic Distribution from ChemDraw:		Theoretical % D for Peak	Corrected Peak Area	Amount (%) of compound at Theoretical % D
1			0,0000E+00	0,0	¹³ C # 2	35,7	0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
2	64,3	2,5000E+01	2,5000E+01	3,5	¹³ C # 3	3,5	64,3	2,5000E+01	5,5
3	71,4	5,7000E+01	4,8075E+01	7,6			71,4	4,8075E+01	10,6
4	78,6	1,3400E+02	1,1278E+02	19,5			78,6	1,1278E+02	24,9
5	85,7	2,2000E+02	1,7017E+02	32,2	Total Corrected Area of all Isotopic Peaks		85,7	1,7017E+02	37,5
6	92,9	1,6200E+02	7,8770E+01	16,1	4,5325E+02		92,9	7,8770E+01	17,4
7	100,0	8,4000E+01	1,8466E+01	4,1			100,0	1,8466E+01	4,1
8			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
9			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
10			0,0000E+00	0,0	Average % Deuteration of Molecule		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
11			0,0000E+00	0,0	83,1		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
12			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
13			0,0000E+00	0,0	Error = +/- 2 %		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
14			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
15			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
16			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
17			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
18			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
19			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
20			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
21			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
22			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
23			0,0000E+00	0,0	Input Data		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
24			0,0000E+00	0,0	Calculated		0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
25			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
26			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
27			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
28			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
29			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0
30			0,0000E+00	0,0			0,0	0,0000E+00	0,0

Figure 6. Calculation of deuteration percentage of the hydrogen atoms in the oxononanoyl-chain based of POND₁₄PC on ESI-MS of OB_135 (excluding aldehydic hydrogen).